

Structure-reactivity correlation in the oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by 2,2'-bipyridinium chlorochromate[†]

Pradeep K. Sharma

Department of Chemistry, J. N. V. University, Jodhpur-342 005, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : drpkvs27@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 19 September 2008, accepted 1 October 2008

Abstract : Oxidation of thirty six monosubstituted benzaldehydes by 2,2'-bipyridinium chlorochromate (BPCC) in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO), leads to the formation of corresponding benzoic acids. The reaction is of first order with respect to both BPCC and aldehydes. The reaction is promoted by hydrogen ions; the hydrogen ion dependence has the form $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$. The oxidation of [²H]benzaldehyde (PhCDO) exhibited a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect. The reaction was studied in nineteen different organic solvents and the effect of solvent was analysed using Taft's and Swain's multi-parametric equations. The rates of the oxidation of *para*- and *meta*-substituted benzaldehydes showed excellent correlation in terms of Charton's triparametric LDR equation, whereas the oxidation of *ortho*-substituted benzaldehydes were correlated well with tetraparametric LDRS equation. The oxidation of *para*-substituted benzaldehydes is more susceptible to the delocalized effect than is the oxidation of *ortho*- and *meta*-substituted compounds, which display a greater dependence on the field effect. The positive value of η suggests the presence of an electron-deficient reaction centre in the rate-determining step. The reaction is subjected to steric acceleration by the *ortho*-substituents. A suitable mechanism has been proposed.

Keywords : Oxidation, 2,2'-bipyridinium chlorochromate, substituted benzaldehydes, correlation studies.

Introduction

Halochromates have been used as mild and selective oxidizing reagents in synthetic organic chemistry¹⁻⁵. 2,2'-Bipyridinium chlorochromate (BPCC) is also one of such compounds used as mild and selective oxidizing agent in synthetic organic chemistry⁶. We have been interested in kinetics of oxidations by Cr^{VI} species and have already published a few reports on oxidation by other pyridinium^{7,8} and quinolinium halochromates^{9,10}. In continuation of our earlier work, we report in the present article the kinetics of oxidation of some monosubstituted benzaldehydes by BPCC in DMSO as solvent. The major objective of this investigation was to study the structure-reactivity correlation for the substrate undergoing oxidation.

Results and discussion

The rates and other experimental data were obtained for all the alcohols. Since the results are similar, only representative data are reproduced here.

Stoichiometry : Oxidation of benzaldehydes by BPCC results in the oxidation of corresponding benzaldehydes. Analysis of products and the stoichiometric determinations indicate the following overall reaction (1).

Thus BPCC undergoes a two electron change. This is in accord with the earlier observations with BPCC⁸ and other halochromates^{9,10}. It has already been shown that both pyridinium fluorochromate (PFC)¹¹ and pyridinium chlorochromate (PCC)¹² act as two electron oxidants and are reduced to chromium(IV) species.

Rate laws : The reactions were found to be first order with respect to BPCC. The individual kinetic runs were strictly first order to BPCC. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , was independent of initial concentration of BPCC. The reaction showed a first order depen-

[†]Dedicated to Professor Suresh C. Ameta on his 60th birthday.

dence on the aldehyde concentration also (Table 1). Fig. 1 depicted a typical kinetic run.

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of benzaldehyde by BPCC at 298 K

10^3 [BPCC] (mol dm ⁻³)	[Aldehyde] (mol dm ⁻³)	[TsOH] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)
1.0	0.10	0.0	1.48
1.0	0.20	0.0	2.90
1.0	0.40	0.0	5.75
1.0	0.60	0.0	8.64
1.0	0.80	0.0	11.7
1.0	1.00	0.0	14.4
1.0	2.00	0.0	29.7
2.0	0.40	0.0	5.52
4.0	0.40	0.0	6.15
6.0	0.40	0.0	5.37
8.0	0.40	0.0	6.04
1.0	0.40	0.0	6.75 ^a

^aContained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

Fig. 1. Oxidation of benzaldehyde by BPCC : A typical kinetic run.

Test for free radicals : The oxidation of benzaldehyde by BPCC, in an atmosphere of nitrogen failed to induce the polymerisation of acrylonitrile. Further, an addition of a radical scavenger, acrylonitrile, had no effect on the rate (Table 1). To further confirm the absence of free radicals in the reaction pathway, the reaction was carried out in the presence of 0.05 mol dm⁻³ of 2,6-di-*t*-butyl-4-methylphenol (butylated hydroxytoluene or BHT). It was observed that BHT was recovered unchanged, almost quantitatively.

Effect of acidity : The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions. The hydrogen ion dependence taking the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$ (Table 1). The values for a and b for benzaldehyde are $14.5 \pm 0.14 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $25.1 \pm 0.23 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively ($r^2 = 0.9997$).

Effect of temperature : The rates of the oxidation of benzaldehydes by BPCC were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 2). The $\log k_2$ at different temperatures is linearly related to the inverse of the temperature in all the cases (Fig. 2). The Arrhenius equation is therefore, valid for this reaction.

Table 2. Dependence of the reaction rate on hydrogen-ion concentration

[Benzaldehyde] 0.10 mol dm ⁻³	[BPCC] 0.001 mol dm ⁻³				Temp. 298 K	
[TsOH] (mol dm ³)	0.10	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80	1.00
$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ¹)	16.9	19.7	24.5	29.3	34.7	39.6

Fig. 2. Oxidation of benzaldehydes by BPCC : Effect of temperature : (◆) H, (■) *o*-Me, (▲) *m*-Me, (×) *o*-I.

Kinetic isotope effect : To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the aldehydic C-H bond in the rate-determining step, oxidation of α,α -dideuterio-benzaldehyde (PhCDO) was studied. Results showed the presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect (Table 2).

Effect of solvents : The oxidation of benzaldehyde was studied in 19 different organic solvents. The choice of solvents was limited by the solubility of BPCC and its reaction with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with the solvents chosen. Kinetics is similar in all the solvents. The values of k_2 are recorded in Table 3.

Table 3. Rate constants and activation parameters of the oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by BPCC

Subst.	$10^4 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
H	5.67	14.4	36.9	89.1	67.5 ± 0.6	-73 ± 2	89.2 ± 0.5
<i>p</i> -Me	12.1	29.6	73.3	171	64.8 ± 0.6	-76 ± 1	87.4 ± 0.5
<i>p</i> -OMe	28.8	68.8	166	378	62.9 ± 0.5	-75 ± 2	85.3 ± 0.4
<i>p</i> -F	6.75	17.4	45.5	108	68.1 ± 0.5	-70 ± 1	88.7 ± 0.4
<i>p</i> -Cl	4.00	10.5	28.1	70.2	70.4 ± 0.4	-66 ± 2	90.0 ± 0.6
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	0.29	0.87	2.63	7.52	80.2 ± 0.2	-54 ± 3	96.1 ± 0.6
<i>p</i> -CF ₃	0.81	2.32	6.63	17.1	75.1 ± 0.1	-63 ± 1	93.7 ± 0.3
<i>p</i> -COOMe	1.07	2.97	8.36	21.6	73.9 ± 0.9	-65 ± 2	93.1 ± 0.5
<i>p</i> -Br	3.89	10.3	27.4	68.4	70.4 ± 0.4	-66 ± 2	89.9 ± 0.4
<i>p</i> -NHAc	13.2	32.8	81.9	189	65.2 ± 0.2	-74 ± 2	87.1 ± 0.4
<i>p</i> -CN	0.51	1.49	4.37	11.7	77.2 ± 0.2	-59 ± 2	94.8 ± 0.4
<i>p</i> -SMe	15.3	38.9	96.3	225	65.8 ± 0.8	-71 ± 1	86.7 ± 0.2
<i>p</i> -NMe ₂	117	270	603	1260	57.9 ± 0.9	-82 ± 1	82.0 ± 0.1
<i>m</i> -Me	9.78	24.2	59.6	135	64.1 ± 0.4	-80 ± 1	87.9 ± 0.3
<i>m</i> -OMe	9.97	23.7	57.0	126	62.1 ± 0.5	-87 ± 2	88.0 ± 0.4
<i>m</i> -Cl	1.80	4.75	12.6	31.5	70.2 ± 0.6	-73 ± 2	92.0 ± 0.5
<i>m</i> -Br	1.78	4.69	12.5	30.6	69.9 ± 0.6	-74 ± 2	91.9 ± 0.5
<i>m</i> -F	2.17	5.64	14.7	36.0	68.9 ± 0.6	-76 ± 2	91.5 ± 0.5
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	0.21	0.63	1.91	5.40	80.1 ± 0.7	-57 ± 2	96.9 ± 0.5
<i>m</i> -CO ₂ Me	1.02	2.82	7.87	20.7	74.0 ± 0.7	-65 ± 2	93.2 ± 0.5
<i>m</i> -CF ₃	0.71	1.99	5.68	15.3	75.6 ± 0.8	-63 ± 3	94.0 ± 0.6
<i>m</i> -CN	0.37	1.08	3.18	8.76	77.9 ± 0.7	-60 ± 2	95.6 ± 0.5
<i>m</i> -SMe	6.93	16.8	41.4	95.4	64.2 ± 0.6	-80 ± 2	88.8 ± 0.4
<i>m</i> -NHAc	6.20	15.2	37.8	88.2	65.0 ± 0.6	-81 ± 3	89.0 ± 0.5
<i>o</i> -Me	44.1	96.3	216	441	56.2 ± 0.5	-95 ± 2	84.5 ± 0.4
<i>o</i> -OMe	38.0	83.7	187	387	56.6 ± 0.4	-95 ± 1	84.8 ± 0.4
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	0.54	1.39	3.87	9.72	71.2 ± 0.9	-80 ± 3	94.9 ± 0.8
<i>o</i> -COOMe	3.63	9.12	22.5	54.0	66.0 ± 0.5	-82 ± 2	90.3 ± 0.4
<i>o</i> -NHAc	51.3	115	243	495	54.6 ± 0.1	-99 ± 1	84.1 ± 0.1
<i>o</i> -Cl	9.45	22.3	52.2	117	61.4 ± 0.5	-90 ± 2	88.1 ± 0.4
<i>o</i> -Br	12.2	28.1	65.4	135	58.8 ± 0.5	-97 ± 1	87.5 ± 0.4
<i>o</i> -I	19.8	45.0	99.0	207	57.1 ± 0.1	-99 ± 1	86.4 ± 0.1
<i>o</i> -CN	1.05	2.79	7.51	18.9	71.0 ± 0.6	-75 ± 2	93.2 ± 0.5
<i>o</i> -SMe	49.5	111	234	477	54.5 ± 0.1	-99 ± 1	84.2 ± 0.1
<i>o</i> -F	5.95	14.6	36.0	83.7	64.7 ± 0.6	-82 ± 2	89.1 ± 0.5
<i>o</i> -CF ₃	7.47	17.5	41.4	90.0	60.9 ± 0.4	-94 ± 1	88.7 ± 0.3
PhCDO	0.95	2.51	6.65	16.7	70.3 ± 0.6	-78 ± 2	93.5 ± 0.5
k_H/k_D	5.97	5.74	5.55	5.34			

The correlation between activation enthalpies and entropies of the oxidation of the thirty six benzaldehydes is not very good ($r^2 = 0.8768$). The value of the isokinetic

temperature is 524 ± 23 K. However, according to Exner¹³, an isokinetic relationship between the calculated values of activation enthalpies and entropies is often vitiated by

random experimental errors. Exner suggested an alternative method for establishing the isokinetic relationship. Exner's plot between $\log k_2$ at 288 K and at 318 K was linear ($r^2 = 0.9976$; Fig. 3). The value of isokinetic temperature evaluated from the Exner's plot is 688 ± 35 K. The linear isokinetic correlation implies that all the alcohols are oxidized by the same mechanism and the changes in the rate are governed by changes in both the enthalpy and entropy of activation.

Fig. 3. Exner's isokinetic relationship in the oxidation of benzaldehydes by BPCC.

The observed hydrogen-ion dependence suggests that the reaction follows two mechanistic pathways, one acid-independent and another acid-dependent. The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of BPCC as eq. (2) to yield a protonated Cr^{VI} species which is a stronger oxidant and electrophile. Formation of a protonated Cr^{VI} species has earlier been postulated in the reactions of structurally similar PCC¹⁴.

The rate constants k_2 , in eighteen solvents (CS_2 was not considered as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) were correlated in terms of linear solvation energy relationship (3) of Kamlet *et al.*¹⁵.

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (3)$$

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, β the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities and α is the hydrogen bond donor acidity. A_0 is the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 13 has a value of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses terms of eq. (3), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β are given below (4)-(7).

$$\log k_2 = -4.17 + 1.51 (\pm 0.20)\pi^* + 0.17 (\pm 0.16)\beta + 0.12 (\pm 0.16)\alpha \quad (4)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8417; \text{sd} = 0.18; n = 18; \psi = 0.44$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.20 + 1.56 (\pm 0.19)\pi^* + 0.13 (\pm 0.15)\beta \quad (5)$$

$$R_2 = 0.8348; \text{sd} = 0.18; n = 18; \psi = 0.43$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.18 + 1.59 (\pm 0.18)\pi^* \quad (6)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8269; \text{sd} = 0.18; n = 18; \psi = 0.43$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.29 + 0.41 (\pm 0.34)\beta \quad (7)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0815; \text{sd} = 0.41; n = 18; \psi = 0.99$$

Here n is the number of data points and ψ is Exner's statistical parameter¹⁶.

Kamlet's¹⁵ triparametric equation explain *ca.* 84% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. However, by Exner's criterion the correlation is not even satisfactory [cf. eq. (4)]. The major contribution is of solvent polarity. It alone accounted for *ca.* 83% of the data. Both β and α play relatively minor roles.

The data on the solvent effect were also analysed in terms of Swain's equation¹⁷ of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents (8).

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (8)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. $(A + B)$ is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of eq. (8), separately with A and B and with $(A + B)$.

$$\log k_2 = 0.59 + (\pm 0.04)A + 1.63 (\pm 0.03)B - 4.39 \quad (9)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9956; \text{sd} = 0.03; n = 19; \psi = 0.07$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.36 (\pm 0.54)A - 3.27 \quad (10)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0260; \text{sd} = 0.43; n = 19; \psi = 1.01$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.58 (\pm 0.11)B - 4.19 \quad (11)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9265; \text{sd} = 0.12; n = 19; \psi = 0.19$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.28 \pm 0.13(A + B) - 4.35 \quad (12)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8439; \text{sd} = 0.17; n = 19; \psi = 0.41$$

The rates of oxidation of benzaldehyde in different solvents showed an excellent correlation in Swain's equation [cf. eq. (9)] with the cation-solvating power playing the major role. In fact, the cation-solvation alone account for *ca.* 93% of the data. The correlation with the anion-solvating power was very poor. The solvent polarity, represented by $(A + B)$, also accounted for *ca.* 84%

of the data. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 85% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r^2 = 0.5436$; $sd = 0.36$; $\psi = 0.72$).

Correlation analysis of reactivity : The effect of structure on reactivity has long been correlated in terms of the Hammett equation¹⁸ or with dual substituent-parameter equations^{19,20}. In the late 1980s, Charton²¹ introduced a triparametric LDR equation for the quantitative description of structural effects on chemical reactivities. This triparametric equation results from the fact that substituent types differ in their mode of electron delocalization.

Here, σ_1 is a localized (field and/or inductive) effect parameter, σ_d is the intrinsic delocalized electrical effect parameter when active site electronic demand is minimal and σ_e represents the sensitivity of the substituent to changes in electronic demand by the active site. The latter two substituent parameters are related by eq. (13).

$$\sigma_D = \eta\sigma_e + \sigma_d \quad (13)$$

Here η represents the electronic demand of the reaction site and is given by $\eta = R/D$, and σ_D represents the delocalized electrical parameter of the diparametric LD equation.

For *ortho*-substituted compounds, it is necessary to account for the possibility of steric effects and

Charton²¹, therefore, modified the LDR equation to generate the LDRS eq. (14).

$$\log k_2 = L\sigma_1 + D\sigma_d + R\sigma_e + Sv + h \quad (14)$$

where v is the well known Charton's steric parameter based on Van der Waals radii²².

The rates of oxidation of *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-substituted benzaldehydes show an excellent correlation in terms of the LDR/LDRS equations (Table 5). We have used the standard deviation (sd), the coefficient of multiple determination (R^2), and Exner's¹⁶ parameter, ψ , as the measures of goodness of fit.

Table 4. Solvent effect on the oxidation of benzaldehyde by BPCC at 308 K

Solvent	$10^4 k_2$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)	Solvent	$10^4 k_2$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)
Chloroform	12.0	Toluene	3.47
1,2-Dichloroethane	14.8	Acetophenone	17.4
Dichloromethane	12.6	Tetrahydrofuran	6.46
Dimethylsulfoxide	36.9	<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	5.25
Acetone	13.2	1,4-Dioxane	6.03
DMF	18.2	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	3.89
Butanone	9.12	Ethyl acetate	4.68
Nitrobenzene	14.5	Carbon disulfide	2.00
Benzene	4.27	Acetic acid	3.39
Cyclohexane	0.54		

Table 5. Temperature dependence for the reaction constants for the oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by BPCC

<i>T</i> /K	<i>L</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>S</i>	η	R^2	<i>sd</i>	ψ	P_D	<i>P</i>
<i>para</i> -Substituted										
288	-1.53	-1.98	-1.17	-	0.59	0.9999	0.004	0.01	56.4	-
298	-1.44	-1.89	-1.12	-	0.59	0.9998	0.001	0.01	56.6	-
308	-1.35	-1.80	-1.06	-	0.58	0.9989	0.001	0.04	57.1	-
318	-1.27	-1.71	-1.01	-	0.59	0.9998	0.007	0.02	57.4	-
<i>meta</i> -Substituted										
288	-1.89	-1.35	-1.07	-	0.79	0.9998	0.002	0.02	41.7	-
298	-1.80	-1.26	-0.98	-	0.78	0.9999	0.001	0.01	41.2	-
308	-1.71	-1.17	-0.91	-	0.77	0.9998	0.001	0.02	40.6	-
318	-1.62	-1.07	-0.83	-	0.78	0.9989	0.004	0.04	39.8	-
<i>ortho</i> -Substituted										
288	-1.86	-1.60	-1.22	1.15	0.76	0.9998	0.009	0.02	46.2	24.9
298	-1.80	-1.53	-1.18	1.08	0.77	0.9999	0.006	0.01	45.9	24.5
308	-1.71	-1.44	-1.04	0.99	0.72	0.9999	0.004	0.01	45.7	23.9
318	-1.64	-1.35	-0.99	0.89	0.73	0.9998	0.005	0.02	45.2	23.0

The comparison of the L and D values for the substituted benzaldehydes showed that the oxidation of *para*-substituted benzaldehydes is more susceptible to the delocalization effect than to the localized effect. However, the oxidation of *ortho*- and *meta*-substituted compounds exhibited a greater dependence on the field effect. In all cases, the magnitude of the reaction constants decreases with an increase in the temperature, pointing to a decrease in selectivity with an increase in temperature.

All three regression coefficients, L , D and R , are negative indicating an electron deficient carbon centre in the activated complex for the rate-determining step. The positive value of η adds a negative increment to σ_d , reflecting the electron donating power of the substituent and its capacity to stabilise a cationic species. The positive value of S indicates that the reaction is subject to steric acceleration by an *ortho*-substituent.

To test the significance of localized, delocalized and steric effects in the *ortho*-substituted benzaldehydes, multiple regression analyses were carried out with (i) σ_1 , σ_d and σ_e , (ii) σ_d , σ_e and ν and (iii) σ_1 , σ_e and ν . The absence of significant correlations showed that all the four substituent constants are significant.

$$\log k_2 = -1.58 (\pm 0.40) \sigma_1 - 1.60 (\pm 0.40) \sigma_d - 3.26 (\pm 1.79) \sigma_e - 2.48 \quad (15)$$

$$R_2 = 0.8448; sd = 0.27; n = 12; \psi = 0.45$$

$$\log k_2 = -1.69 (\pm 0.46) \sigma_d - 1.75 (\pm 2.86) \sigma_e + 0.79 (\pm 0.53) \nu - 3.40 \quad (16)$$

$$R_2 = 0.6562; sd = 0.27; n = 12; \psi = 0.73$$

$$\log k_2 = -2.03 (\pm 0.65) \sigma_1 - 0.38 (\pm 3.12) \sigma_e + 1.21 (\pm 0.58) \nu - 2.55 \quad (17)$$

$$R_2 = 0.5898; sd = 0.44; n = 12; \psi = 0.73$$

Similarly in the cases of the oxidation of *para*- and *meta*-substituted benzaldehydes, multiple regression analyses indicated that both localization and delocalization effects are significant. There is no significant collinearity between the various substituents constants for the three series.

The percent contribution¹⁹ of the delocalized effect, P_D , is given by following eq. (18).

$$P_D = (|D| \times 100) / (|L| + |D|) \quad (18)$$

Similarly, the percent contribution of the steric parameter²² to the total effect of the substituent, P_S , was determined by using eq. (18).

$$P_S = (|S| \times 100) / (|L| + |D| + |S|) \quad (19)$$

The values of P_D and P_S are also recorded in Table 5.

The value of P_D for the oxidation of *para*-substituted benzaldehydes is *ca.* 56% whereas the corresponding values for the *meta*- and *ortho*-substituted alcohols are *ca.* 42 and 46% respectively. This shows that the balance of localization and delocalization effects is different for differently substituted benzaldehydes. The less pronounced resonance effect from the *ortho*-position than from the *para*-position may be due to the twisting away of the alcoholic group from the plane of the benzene ring. The magnitude of the P_S value shows that the steric effect is significant in this reaction.

The positive value of S showed a steric acceleration of the reaction. This may be explained on the basis high ground state energy of the sterically crowded alcohols. Since the crowding is relieved in the product aldehyde as well as the transition state leading to it, the transition state energy of the crowded and uncrowded alcohols do not differ much and steric acceleration, therefore results.

Mechanism :

A hydrogen abstraction mechanism leading to the formation of the free radicals is unlikely in view of the failure to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile and no effect of the radical scavenger on the reaction rate. The presence of a substantial kinetic isotope effect confirms the cleavage of a aldehydic C-H bond in the rate-determining step. The negative values of the localization and delocalization electrical effects i.e. of L , D and R points to an electron deficient reaction centre in the rate-determining step. It is further supported by the positive value of η , which indicates that the substituent is better able to stabilise a cationic or electron-deficient reactive site. Therefore, a hydride ion transfer in the rate-determining step is suggested. The hydride-ion transfer mechanism is also supported by the major role of cation-solvating power of the solvents.

The hydride ion transfer may take place either by a cyclic process via an ester intermediate or by an acyclic one-step bimolecular process. Kwart and Nickle²³ have shown that a dependence of kinetic isotope effect on temperature can be gainfully employed to determine whether the loss of hydrogen proceeds through a concerted cyclic process or by an acyclic one. The data for protio- and deuterio-benzyl alcohols, fitted to the familiar expression : $k_H/k_D = A_H/A_D (-\Delta H^*/RT)^{24,25}$ show a direct correspondence of a symmetrical transition state in which activation energy difference for protio and deuterio compounds is equal to the difference in the zero-point energy for the respective C-H and C-D bonds ($\approx 4.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) and the entropies of activation of the

respective reactions are almost equal. Similar phenomena were also observed earlier in the oxidation of benzhydrol by BTEACC¹² and of hydroxy acids by QFC¹⁰. Bordwell²⁶ has documented a very cogent evidence against the occurrence of concerted one-step bimolecular processes by hydrogen transfer and it is evident that in the present studies also the hydrogen transfer does not occur by an acyclic biomolecular process. It is well-established that intrinsically concerted sigmatropic reactions, characterised by transfer of hydrogen in a cyclic transition state, are the only truly symmetrical processes involving a linear hydrogen transfer²⁷. Litler²⁸ has also shown that a cyclic hydride transfer, in the oxidation of alcohols by Cr^{VI}, involves six electrons and, being a Hückel-type system, is an allowed process. Thus, a transition state having a planar, cyclic and symmetrical structure can be envisaged for the decomposition of the ester intermediate. Hence, the overall mechanism is proposed to involve the formation of a chromate ester in a fast pre-equilibrium step and then a decomposition of the ester in a subsequent slow step via a cyclic concerted symmetrical transition state leading to the product (Schemes 1 and 2).

Acid-independent Path

Scheme 1

Acid-independent Path

Scheme 2

The observed negative value of entropy of activation also supports the proposed mechanism. As the charge separation takes place in the transition state, the charged ends become highly solvated. This results in an immobilization of a large number of solvent molecules, reflected in the loss of entropy²⁹.

Experimental

Materials : BPCC was prepared by reported method⁶ and its purity was checked by iodometric method. The aldehydes were commercial products. The liquid aldehydes were purified through their bisulfite addition compounds and distilling them, under nitrogen, just before use³⁰. The solid aldehydes were recrystallized from ethanol. Deuteriated benzaldehyde (PhCDO) was also prepared by the reported method³¹. Its isotopic purity, as ascertained by its NMR spectrum, was $96 \pm 5\%$. Due to non-aqueous nature of the solvent, toluene-*p*-sulphonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. Solvents were purified by the usual methods.

Product analysis : The product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. In a typical experiment, benzaldehyde (5.25 g, 0.05 mol) and BPCC (3.10 g, 0.01 mol) were made up to 50 cm³ in DMSO and kept in the dark for *ca.* 15 h to ensure completion of the reaction. The solution was then treated with an excess (200 cm³) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in 2 mol dm⁻³ HCl and kept overnight in a refrigerator. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, weighed, recrystallized from ethanol, and weighed again. The yields of DNP before and after recrystallization were 2.52 g (88%) and 2.32 g (81%) respectively. The DNP was found identical (m.p. and mixed m.p.) with the DNP of benzaldehyde. Similar experiments were performed with other alcohols also. The oxidation state of chromium in completely reduced reaction mixtures, determined by an iodometric method was 3.95 ± 0.15 .

Kinetic measurements : The pseudo-first order conditions were attained by maintaining a large excess ($\times 15$ or more) of the alcohol over BPCC. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed, at constant temperatures (± 0.1 K), by monitoring the decrease in [BPCC] spectrophotometrically at 365 nm. No other reactant or product has any significant absorption at this wavelength. The pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , was evaluated from the linear ($r = 0.990-0.999$) plots of $\log [\text{BPCC}]$ against time for

up to 80% reaction. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within 3%. The second order rate constant, k_2 , was obtained from the relation : $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{aldehyde}]$. All experiments, other than those for studying the effect of hydrogen ions, were carried out in the absence of TsOH.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to UGC, New Delhi for financial support. MRP No. F. 32-207/2006 (SR) and to Professor Kalyan K. Banerji, Dean, Sciences, National Law University, Jodhpur, for his critical suggestions.

References

1. E. J. Corey and W. J. Suggs, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1975, 2647.
2. C. S. Rao, A. A. Deshmukh, M. R. Thakor and P. S. Srinivasan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1986, **25**, 324.
3. M. N. Bhattacharjee, M. K. Choudhuri, H. S. Dasgupta, N. Roy and D. T. Khathing, *Synthesis*, 1982, 588.
4. K. Balasubramanian and V. Prathiba, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1986, **25**, 326.
5. A. Pandurangan, V. Murugesan and P. Palamichamy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1995, **72**, 479.
6. F. S. Guziec and F. A. Luzio, *Synthesis*, 1980, 691.
7. R. Khanchandani, K. K. Banerji and P. K. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 42.
8. R. Kumbhat and V. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 745.
9. O. Prakash and P. K. Sharma, *Oxid. Commun.*, 2003, **26**, 517.
10. S. Vyas and P. K. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **80**, 820.
11. H. C. Brown, G. C. Rao and S. U. Kulkarni, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1979, **44**, 2809.
12. M. N. Bhattacharjee, M. K. Choudhuri and S. Purakayastha, *Tetrahedron*, 1987, **43**, 5389.
13. O. Exner, *Collect. Chem. Czech. Commun.*, 1964, **29**, 1094.
14. S. Saraswat, V. Sharma and K. K. Banerji, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 583.
15. M. J. Kamlet, J. L. M. Abboud, M. H. Abraham and R. W. Taft, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1983, **48**, 2877 and references cited therein.
16. O. Exner, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1966, **31**, 3222.
17. C. G. Swain, M. S. Swain, A. L. Powel and S. Alunni, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **105**, 502.
18. C. D. Johnson, "The Hammett Equation", University Press, Cambridge, 1973, 78.
19. S. Ehrenson, R. T. C. Brownlee and R. W. Taft, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **96**, 9113.
20. C. G. Swain, S. H. Unger, N. R. Rosenquest and M. S. Swain, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **105**, 492.
21. M. Charton and B. Charton, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1988, 199 and references cited therein.
22. M. Charton, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1975, **40**, 407.
23. H. Kwart and J. H. Nickel, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **95**, 3394.
24. H. Kwart and M. C. Latimer, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **93**, 3770.
25. H. Kwart and J. Slutsky, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1972, 1182.
26. F. G. Bordwell, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1974, **5**, 374.
27. R. W. Woodward and R. Hoffmann, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Eng.*, 1969, **8**, 781.
28. J. S. Littler, *Tetrahedron*, 1971, **27**, 81.
29. E. S. Gould, "Mechanism and Structure in Organic Chemistry". Holt, Rinehart & Winston Inc., New York, 1964.
30. J. Kalpan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 2639.
31. K. B. Wiberg, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 5871.